

A GEOGRAPHICAL REVIEW OF MOHOL PERIODIC MARKET

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Abstract

In various fields of geography, economic geography has experienced remarkable changes within the past thirty years resulting in diverse specialized branches such as geography of agriculture, industry, transportation marketing etc. All these branches are related to the study of great variations on the earth's surface in means economic activities.

Marketing is a part of mans economic activity it deals with the marketing activity. Economic geography has considerable attention on the study of resources and factors of production associated with market places and marketing.

Marketing geography is a branch of economic geography which seeks a specialized study of marketing places and marketing. Marketing geography deals with the application of the geographical principles, methods and techniques to the practical problems related to the marketing phenomena.

In the present paper an analysis has been made to study the problems of weekly

(periodic) market centers of Mohol and weekly market centers play process, mediating exchanger between farmers and craft manufactures for sellers and traders on the other hand urban wholesalers.

Key Words : periodic, market, economic activity, retail-wholesale trade

Introduction:

The origin and development of marketing and market places are closely associated with development of man's activity, and the history of civilization. The simple unorganized and rudimentary trader on exchange of commodities is as old as man's society. Although the earliest man believed in self-sufficient and had no idea either of exchange of goods. It is very limited wants were satisfied either by his immediate environment or the place he used to move in search of food, water favorable climate or remained unfulfilled. This nomadic culture too have occasional free exchange of gifts or reciprocal exchange of needed items with the growth of social contact and when man started living in groups, he began the practice of exchange of commodities "Accidental surpluses, specialization of production. Presence of a rare and desirable item or the need for essential products, gave rise to the exchange of goods which in turn man made man enlarged his knowledge of good and his desire to obtain them.

The Study Region:

The study region Mohol is a one of the important aspect agricultural tahsil of Solapur district, lies between 17⁰45' North Latitude and 75⁰35' East Longitude, and a Railway station on the Pune-Solapur broad-guage line of the south central railway. The Hyderabad-Pune National Highway No. 13 pass out in the central of Mohol town and tahsil of Solapur district.

Aims and Objectives:

In the present paper an analysis has been made to study the problems of weekly (periodic) market centers of Mohol and weekly market centers play process, mediating

exchanger between farmers and craft manufactures for sellers and traders on the other hand urban wholesalers. The aims and objectives of the present study are:

1. To study the commodity structure and marketing system.
2. To study the trading activities under the fabric of marketing geography.
3. To study the location of retail and wholesale trade establishment.
4. To study the marketing territories and facts of trading institution.
5. To observe the services of private business enterprises.
6. To study the distribution of goods required by consumer.
7. To study the various problem of weekly market centers.

Sources of Data:

The entire work is based on the primary and secondary data. Primary data is called from the field work, visiting market center, the personal interviews etc.

The secondary data has been collected from census handbook, Solapur District Socio-Economic Abstract.

Besides this the required data and information has been collected from various books and journals.

Methodology:

The present work has been largely based on field work to collect primary data field workers as well as empirical method has been used to depict the various places of farm sellers of market areas. After collecting the primary data it has been tabulated and represented with the help of statistical techniques and cartographic techniques to show different types of information. The analysis and interpretation of data has been done from the geographical point of view.

Mohol is the one of the important tahsil which is located at the centre of the Solapur district at 460m mean sea level. The Pune-Solapur-Hyderabad (N.H.9) passing through out in

Mohol city and tahsil. Mohol covers an area of 1408 sq.km and involved 104 villages. According to 2001 census the total population of Mohol tahsil is 2,52,526 and the density of the population is 179 people per sq.km.

Morphology of Weekly Market Centers in Mohol:

Mohol weekly market is situated around the Grampanchayat and Annabhahu Sathe Nagar. Where mainly found vegetable stalls. There are permanent stalls, like general stores, kirana stores sweet marts, hairdressers and vegetables stalls etc. Fruits stalls and hotels found mainly outside the road.

In Mohol market intensely vegetable stalls are found where people from surrounding area come to sell their vegetable in periodic market of Mohol at Grampanchayat road.

The shop which controls the morphology and trading in a weekly market, large number of shops in a weekly market more will be trade and large will be market. Weekly market in the region under study is a day affair. It generally starts its function early in the morning from 10 a.m. to 6 p.m. mainly most of traders reach there at 1.00 pm to 3.00 pm. It is largely depends on season.

An intensive survey of hourly variation has been conducted at 10 weekly markets. The total number of stalls has been counted from 1 pm to 6 pm. After each hour the total number has been obtained this includes stalls already counted in previous hour and still continue to exist. For example, there are more than 80 stalling at am, at 12 pm there are addition more the 120 stalls. The actual arrangement of shops starts between 11 am to 12 noon and reached to its peak at 3 pm. More than 90 percent shops used to start transaction at 3 pm. Although between 11 am to 12 pm there is an increase in number of shops. But these shopkeepers are not those who come to attend weekly market from long distance. Generally these are producers. Sellers who brought small quantity of agricultural products which are in great demand to local people. The number of stalls after 3 pm has not been counted because there is no increase in number of stall due to the start of dispersal.

Commodity structure:

General classification of commodity skies in weekly market has been done in the following manner.

A. Agriculture Products:

- i. Food grains, pulses and oil seeds,
- ii. Vegetables and fruits
- iii. Tobacco

B. Animal and Animal Products:

- i. Animalii. Meat
- iii. Hides
- iv. Ghee

C. Other Food Articles

- i. Oil soya been groundnut, sunflower til etc.
- ii. Sweets
- iii. Salt
- iv. Spices

D. Forest Products:

- i. Firewood
- ii. Honey
- iii. Glue
- iv. Other products

E. Manufactured Goods:

- i. Mill made cloth
- ii. Readymade Garments
- iii. Hosiery Articles
- iv. Fancy Goods
- v. Soups
- vi. Plastic Goods
- vii. Aluminium wire

F. Service Shops:

- i. Barbers
- ii. Carpenters
- iii. Black-smiths
- iv. Cycle repair
- v. Lock Repair
- vi. Shoe repair

Commodity wise No. of Stalls in Market Centers

No.	Nature of Commodity	Percentage
1	Vegetables	42.11%
2	Grocery	7.89%
3	Cloths	8.94%
4	Preachers	4.21%
5	Fruits	23.69%
6	Agencies	2.63%
7	Others	10.53%
	Total:	100%

Marketing Process:

Throughout the Mohol marketing process weekly market is common. Basically the marketing system in these markets are simple and direct. The profit is the primary motive of both traders and consumers. Therefore there is much haggling in prices and one can see too much variations of the prices in same products in early and late hours of marketing on market day and sometime at different shops at the same time.

Marketing Process in Weekly Markets

The Consumer's behavior Pattern

Weekly and bi-weekly markets are the only means for satisfying the need of local people. Use nearest market centers for meeting their requirement. The consumers are aware about the market location and market days in their surrounding area and they make their choice according to their level of knowledge. It is only on special occasions that the consumers travel distant market centre for meeting the requirement of their social occasions that the consumers travel distant market center for meeting the requirement or their social, cultural religious and administrative needs.

The consumers behavior pattern is influenced by the mode of transport, quality and availability of goods in market area in context of Mohol weekly market centers, most of the consumers are meetings to Solapur, Kurul market because most of sellers came to sell their goods in these market centers.

The service area of market centers are influenced by their functional importance. The spacing between market centers size of market centers is the important factors which affects the zone of influence or services areas of the market centers. The transport system serving weekly market place are vital for the circulation of main material or of weekly places give rist to processing of farm produce for marketing them.

Mohol is rural area and has old weekly market place. It serves more area and number of lower order market centers.

Periodic Marketing have many problems. These problems are varying from place to place. These problems are governing authoress, farm-sellers, buyers or consumers, middlemen or agent and also have socio-economic in nature. Some of the important problem of Mohol weekly market centers as follows:

Problems of Market Centers:

The following are the problems of market centers.

1. Seller-consumers transport problems.
2. Problem of storage facility.
3. Middle man agent as a problem.
4. Suitable place for marketing.
5. Drinking water problem
6. Garbage cleaning
7. Shortage place of wholesale market
8. Agricultural marketing problem
9. Absence of co-operative societies of farmers

Conclusion:

Marketing is concerned with location and distribution of markets, their infrastructure pattern, marketing activities, movement of commodities consumer behavior and order to prepare a systematic plan for regional development. Periodic market play a key role in the internal trading processes, mediating exchange between farmers, craft manufactures for stalls.

The weekly market of Mohol is held on Sunday. The size of market is big because Mohol is taluka place. There is some temporary and permanent shops i.e. fish, meat, general stalls, grocery shops etc. Mohol periodic market have many problems such as governing authorities farm sellers, buyers and agents.

References

1. H.M. Saxena, 1984, Geography of Marketing, Sterling Publishing Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
2. David J. Luck, Ronald S. Rubin, 1987, Marketing Research, Prentic Hall Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi
3. Indra Singh, 2006, Economic Geography, Alfa Publication, New Delhi.
4. Truman A. Hartshorn and John W. Alexander, 2004, Economic Geography, Prentic Hall of India, New Delhi.
5. Solapur Sensus 1991
6. Gazetteer 2001
7. Dixit R. S., 1988, Special Organization of Market Center, Pointer Publisher Jaipur.
8. Cambrial, 1975, Periodic Market and Rural Development Policy, Vol.2,
9. www.gis.nic.com

10. www.mapping.com

11. www.geography

berkelcy.edu

